

Temporal Transformation of Materials: Can Designers Harness the Effects of Time to Create a Contemporary Aesthetic of ‘Worldliness’ within New Products?

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Abstract

Like human beings, earthly materials age. They weather; their skins show wear and tear and the ravages of time. This worldly effect has created cultural value systems that cover the full grey scale of emotion and aesthetic from ‘beautiful’ to ‘ugly’. ‘Patina’ describes an altered physical surface but also implies provenance or authenticity. But equally, transience of surface is interpreted less positively in other materials or by other peoples: patina may simply imply the pejorative of ‘old’. Quirks of history, society and culture have meant that some materials are not granted the space to grow old gracefully. Damage to the brand-new lustre of many modern plastics for instance, often implies irreparable damage and therefore disposal.

This is a complex and important field for designers interested in extending the emotional and social life of products. This paper communicates aspects of the research of a group based in UK and in Finland, who are collaborating to establish the foundations of the study of temporality in materials. Research involves the observation of transformation over time in different classes of materials but also peoples’ attitudes and responses to them. The authors will establish research context, key issues and report on findings to date

Keywords: affect, custodianship, haptics, lifecycle, materials, memory, surface, transformation, time.

Temporal value systems and Fashion

In the 21st century Fashion is ubiquitous. Its ever backwards looping cycle means that it has been used and reused in symbolic representation of temporality and now it can be argued that the makers and users of fashion have almost completely undermined temporal cachet. Lee describes our relationship with it as ‘McFashion’, she says: ‘In our “I want it now” world, fashion has begun to resemble fast food: fast, disposable, easy, unthreatening, entertaining and largely homogenous’ (Lee, 2003). She proposes that although it is easy and quick, it is unsustainable and ultimately highly disposable. ‘McFashion’ issues can be identified throughout the consumer’s world, and today we live in a constant state of the present in terms of the products we buy. Material objects have an ability to speak to us about who we are, so will this constant living in the moment lead to memory loss?

The temporal relationship between products and cultural value is a complex and important field for designers hoping to extend the emotional life of new products. A more profound understanding will provide possibilities for innovative design approaches and perhaps for more sustainable patterns of consumption. In order to learn more, two Design schools who share a belief in meaningful relationships between design and materials, decided to collaborate. We are based at the University of Central Lancashire in UK and The Kuopio Academy of Design in Finland and have been working together to establish the foundations of the study of temporality in objects and materials since 2003.

Products and time: pleasure/dissatisfaction cycles

Like other social observers Woolley also draws our attention to the short pleasure/dissatisfaction cycles associated with contemporary, unsustainable patterns of consumption and of the potential environmental destruction that this will cause.

	Phase	Pleasure	Change	Outcome
1.	Pre- purchase	Anticipation	Growing pleasure	Arousal
2.	Short-term	Exploration	Optimum pleasure	Excitement
3.	Medium-term	Application	Decreasing pleasure	Assimilation
4.	Long-term	Use	Pleasure to dissatisfaction	Disinterest or boredom
DISPOSAL OR RETENTION				
5.	Beyond	Satisfaction	Lifetime pleasure in ownership	Respect

Figure 1, Pleasure and Use. (Woolley, 2003)

His concern is with the ongoing movement ‘from long-term ownership to shorter and shorter cycles of pleasure-through-purchase’. (Woolley, 2003: 77-82). He maps a typical product pleasure/dissatisfaction cycle over time, in five phases (figure 1):

The table identifies the diminishing nature of product/owner relationships over time. We have identified phase 5 as being of particular relevance to our project, where objects have become part of someone's life for a significant amount of time. This phase is where the full richness of long term relationships may be studied. Objects may already be heirlooms, where an important relationship has developed during its time with a prior owner, or are heirlooms in the making. In order to find orientation to the emotions that encourage us to keep an object in our lives, the researchers thought it would be useful to draw on personal experiences and so each group member considered a personally cherished object. Here is a selection from their responses.

Cherished objects

My Easy Chair (figure 2): Upholstered easy chair, metal springs on wooden frame, wooden legs, stuffing, cotton cloth covering. Date: circa 1920/1930

Figure 2, the easy chair today

This is a story about a robust easy chair that once was owned by my grandparents and has now been with me for over 20 years. This chair was originally obtained through some exchange deal by my grandfather had after World War 2. It was upholstered in a peculiar fashion with at least three different cloths due to the shortage of suitable materials after the war. In my grandparents' home it was situated in the library corner communicating that this

was the place to sit down and immerse oneself into some interesting book in peace and quiet. For a little girl it was immense and offered real shelter.

When I started to study in another town my grandfather had already died and I was given this chair as a gift for my student accommodation. I think my grandmother and mother guessed that I would just love to have this chair, as at the time I was very enthusiastic about old furniture and nostalgic style. That interest in nostalgia was soon over but still this chair is my companion and I can not be parted from it. After being with me for 15 years the chair was already rather worn out and I had difficulties in keeping it in my own library room. This is why I started a rather long project of getting the chair repaired. First the inside was repaired by a student group learning restoration in my institution. Then it stood in the school attic above my office for some years before I bought a beautiful, modern Italian fabric from the UK where we lived with my family for a year. Still after that it took almost a year for me to have the easy chair upholstered. Now I have this inviting looking set of furniture beside the fireplace in my library room. I feel it was really worth the trouble of having the chair repaired and even the restoration process and the new fabric entangles in my life in many ways. In addition to all the history and memories the easy chair reminds me of, I can still connect with its original use in my grandparents' house. It offers a chance to sit down and relax with a good book or poetry. I actually manage to do this very seldom, but even seeing the chair and thinking about this possibility is very comforting. I have that place in case of need for that kind of uplifting experience. (Mirja Kalviainen)

My Father's War Time Log Book (figure 3): Small blue book, nearly falling apart. Cotton cover frayed and worn in places. The pages are browning and full of an almost indecipherable longhand, written in red, blue and black. Date: 1941

Figure 3, war time memories

When I was a child the book looked like any another in the bookcase, no more aged or worn than most. But even then, the book *felt* different. I remember feeling a certain degree of reverence when I removed it from its shelf and leafed through its pages. Typically my attraction would be triggered by a wartime movie that I had just seen on the TV, or by some related topic that we had been introduced to in history class. My father seemed to look on my constant referencing of the book with some sort of benign amusement, sometimes passing a casual comment regarding the operational performance of a Lancaster or Stirling bomber.

As I grew older, my fascination with the logbook increased and it seemed to change from representing a record of my father's activities in the Air Force, to provide in some strange way a manifestation of my father himself. As an object the book is unremarkable; it represents standard manufacturing processes and materials for a hard back, stitched book. Perhaps then its simple and honest construction has contributed to its longevity. The fabric covering may have given protection, its finish providing some resilience to dirt and moisture. The pages are soft to the touch and perhaps a little too absorbent for a fountain pen; the paper was probably all that was available in those difficult times.

It had always struck me that my father's activities during the war were something that he never bothered to talk about. He still attends the town cenotaph every 11th of November

wearing his carefully polished Distinguished Flying Cross. He seems simply to view it as something he did because his country required him to, just like the hundreds of thousands of others. But this dislocation of a spoken narrative has caused me to continue to be fascinated with the book, partly for its physical qualities as a tangible object and partly because it represents a record of an otherwise absent period in my version of my father's life. My father is a warm man, but I have realised that the logbook represents a metaphor for his lack of sentiment. Whether this is the result of what is described in the book, or a born disposition I do not know, I have never been brave enough to ask him, as part of me thinks I have no business to. (Simon Somerville)

My Mother's Scarves (figure 4): 20 printed headscarves, various sizes, square and rectangular. Multi coloured, 100% polyester crepe or polyester satin. Date: 1975 –2000.

Very sadly, my mother died in 2001. I quickly realised that as well as some other simple things of hers, I wanted to have her collection of scarves. My mum, Irene Frances, was a politician. Like other women of her generation she'd had to pioneer a more feminine version of the predominantly masculine image of the politician in order to present a convincing appearance of authority and effectiveness in her chosen realm of activity.

Figure 4, Irene and some of her scarves.

A decorative, printed silken scarf provided an acceptably gendered alternative to the masculine necktie, and over the years she made a significant collection.

Nearly three years later, this collection of pieces of coloured fabric is still almost overwhelming in its ability to summon her up for me, to recreate a living sense of her. Most of them are bright coloured and involve bold patterns that impact on the senses as visual metaphors of her personal and professional dynamism. Others are quieter, more muted in their colouring and I interpret these as representing her more introspective feelings, or the necessary equipment for more subdued occasions. The accumulation of scarves represents not just her personal aesthetic, but also her differing moods expressed abstractly as pattern and colour. They are all unremarkable in design terms – prosaic, mass-produced polyester scarves.

Quite recently I took another opportunity to experience them, to magic her up in my living room, and I discovered that two scarves had – small holes! At first I feared that I had somehow allowed the holes through negligence. Then I realised that they were not torn or worn holes, they had a slight crust around their edges and so must have been melted by the heat of an iron. Polyester was originally invented to emulate the sensuous handle of silk, but also to replace its frailty and tendency to crease with the synthetic's state of constant perfection. So I realised with a confused sense of relief that she must have made the holes herself. I imagined they had happened when ironing at speed, rushing to get ready for an important meeting or maybe before the iron had cooled down enough after a big load of household ironing.

I was pleased. The scarves already meant more to me than mere objects bought from a shop, but discovering the holes added to remembrance by making past time visible, tangible and telling. The slight imperfections brought animation to otherwise inert polyester and evidenced the disorder of a real life. (Fiona Candy)

Custodial relationships

When reviewing the written accounts we saw that each author had described an important 'custodial' relationship: *Custodian n* 'somebody who wants to protect and uphold something seen as valuable and endangered, for example traditions or moral values' (Collins). 'One who has the custody of a thing or person; a guardian, keeper' (OED). The objects stimulated highly personal memories and held meanings that went way beyond their objective materiality. In one case the object has been restored several times, like a chameleon taking on

a succession of different surfaces, but in the others, established imperfections validate the continuity of the relationship. In all three cases, the passing of time has made the objects special to their owners and is evidenced through material transformation. But, as Woolley points out, only very few objects make it through the pleasure dissatisfaction cycle to be valued and cared for by a custodian. Damage to the brand-new lustre of many modern plastics for instance, often implies irreparable damage and therefore disposal. Can plastic gain a different temporal aesthetic and cultural value?

Other value systems: wabi sabi

A different temporal aesthetic value system evolved in the ancient civilisations of the East. In Japan 'wabi sabi' is a beauty of things imperfect, impermanent, and incomplete.

Juniper (2003), admits that wabi sabi 'is an aesthetic philosophy so intangible and so shrouded in centuries of mystery that even the most ambitious Japanese scholars would give it a wide berth and uphold the Japanese tradition of talking about it only in the most poetic of terms'.

Koren attempts to juxtapose the aesthetic value systems of wabi sabi with those of modernism in the West (figure 5). Unlike many western Hellenic-inspired concepts of beauty, wabi sabi has nothing to do with grandeur or symmetry. The concepts of wabi-sabi correlate with the concepts of Zen Buddhism, as the first Japanese involved with wabi-sabi were tea masters, priests, and monks who practiced Zen. It is possibly the most evident and characteristic feature of what we think of as traditional Japanese beauty and 'occupies roughly the same position in the Japanese pantheon of aesthetic values as do the Greek ideals of beauty and perfection in the West.' (Koren, 1994).

MODERNISIM	WABI SABI
World-view is logical, rational	World-view is intuitive
Absolute	Relative
Universal, prototypical solutions	Personal, idiosyncratic solutions
Mass produced/modular	One of a kind/variable
Faith in progress	There is no progress
Future orientated	Present orientated
Control of nature	Uncontrollability of nature
Romanticises technology	Romanticises nature
People adapting to machines	People adapting to nature
Geometric organisation of form	Organic organisation of form
The box as metaphor	The bowl as metaphor
Artificial materials	Natural materials
Ostensibly 'slick'	Ostensibly 'crude'
Needs to be well maintained	Accommodates to degradation and attrition
Intolerance of ambiguity and contradiction	Comfortable with ambiguity and contradiction

Figure 5, modernism v wabi sabi (edited from Koren, 1994)

Wabi sabi respects transience in objects and materials as an embodiment of life itself. We wondered if empathy for wabi sabi could help designers consider new forms of temporal aesthetic within materials and products, and this led us to initiate a series of student projects during the autumn semester 2003.

Wabi sabi student orientation projects

We asked UK students to search for examples of wabi sabi in their daily lives by looking at all kinds of materials e.g. wood, metal, textiles and ceramics. In Finland students were asked to look specifically at plastic objects and their surfaces.

Results of orientation task: in Finland

Product Design students in the Kuopio Academy of Design were asked to analyse the wearing and durability of a variety of different plastic products. They were asked to search for and document examples that they considered beautiful or ugly. Students quickly found lots of products that were broken, unhygienic and considered as ugly or ‘tacky’. Here they found scratches, dirt and other forms of deterioration in the materials’ surfaces. They found that low care of the cheap and unimportant products around us seem to be the fate of many plastic products. Ironically, in some cases these products have not been tossed away but stay in use even in a broken and otherwise unpleasant condition, as though both the object and the damage are invisible.

Figure 6, examples of cherished, nostalgic plastic objects

Only some examples were considered to show ‘beautiful’ ageing and these were found in prominent important places in the home (figure 6). On the whole these were older products where form and careful production methods produced nostalgic connotations. The older plastic materials were seen to age more beautifully than the more mass-produced, newer ones. They were also heavier and felt more valuable. Nostalgic ageing seems also to be connected with how the product has been handled and preserved, and if it has been in an important relationship with the users. A product in everyday use can be something that is in an important place and decently or even lovingly handled (a phone or a toy) or something that is cheap and just for some practical purpose (a trash bin) and is more roughly handled and gets a lot of scratches or gets broken.

We saw that the surface of plastic wears differently in different products. For example, we found water erosion causing cracks; brownish colour changes in the surface of the product caused by dirt in the air; light causing changes in the pigments and thus fading of colours or just repetitive mechanical use that caused scratches and other signs of attrition in the surface. We found that that in many cases these surface changes created interesting patterns and colours that could be enjoyed if the form or purpose of the product was otherwise obscured i.e. if the viewer was unaware that they were looking at a plastic surface.

In Finland where there are so many wooden products, it was felt that wood made a useful comparison point with plastic. In our studies of experiences from natural materials people have said that they feel that wood ages beautifully. They feel that it is alive and the changes on its surface belong to the natural circle of its life and are therefore understandable and pleasurable. But it seems that plastic is felt to be unnatural, man-made and no changes are allowed as they are in wood.

Results of orientation task: in the UK

Groups of Surface Pattern students were asked to find and document examples of the effects of time on objects and surfaces. Students worked in groups each of which undertook to examine a particular class of material e.g. textile, wood, metal, ceramic/glass. They were free to look at any class of object. Students collected physical samples where possible, took photographs and interviewed people about their feelings towards differing objects and surfaces. They were asked to examine the physical processes at work in order to be able to reapply them creatively in future projects.

	Positive, custodial responses: (cultural meanings/interpretations)	Description of material transformation over time: a. man-made	Description of material transformation over time: b. natural/organic
1.	Adoration: Love, worship, respect, care for, maintain, protect, restore, personal values, cherish.	Polish, patina, tarnish, careful restoration, effects of touching, handling, careful cleaning, precious.	Invisible mending, thread-bare patches,
2.	Nostalgia: memory, family, provenance, history, identity, heritage, safe haven	Tarnish, patina, damage, marks left unrestored, effects of touching, handling, carefully stored, wrapped, odour.	Odour, maturation, fragile, discoloured, staining, yellowing, torn, creasing, fold marks, corners turned over.
3.	Respect for nature: living object, connection to earth, lineage, sense of place, identity, soothing.	Effects of environment over time, sun, rain, water, wind, frost etc. rusting, fading, pitting, porous surfaces, peeling, degrading, base material exposed.	Porous surfaces, slow erosion, bleaching, drying, cracking, warping, shrinking, shrivelling, invasion by living organisms, growth, bruising, subtle deformation, odour.
4.	Respect for function: order, tough, admiration of hard work, reliable, trustworthy, utilitarianism, effective, useful.	Attrition, scoured, removal of applied surface finish, base material exposed, matt and shine, rough handling, nicks and chips, oiled, areas of wear and tear	Torn, worn thin, pilling, fraying, worn away, patched, scrubbed, washed, clean.
5.	Respect for serendipity/ life's challenges: lucky, unlucky, careless, carefree, unconcerned, hedonism	Broken, dented, scratched, signs of obvious repair, accidental damage, eccentric combinations.	Self-healing, subtle signs of repair, darned, patched.
6.	Subversion: making own mark, deface, customise, tame, submit to ownership.	Graffiti, carving of initials, stickers, tagging etc, accumulation of own marks or of others, augmentation	Evident deformation, torn, graffiti, carving of initials, stickers, tagging etc, accumulation of own marks or of others, augmentation

Figure 7, ‘surface effect and affect’ - materials/transformation/cultural interpretations

We then asked student groups to combine their observations and summarise findings. They were asked to define potential custodial qualities and to create a matrix of ‘surface effect and affect’.

We found that a strict classification system is probably impossible to achieve: we learned that materials are perceived in different ways depending on their employment as objects. Although this was a useful exercise in organising our research, we are aware of many overlaps and contradictions, and of biases that creep in through the use of qualitative adjectives.

Objects cannot be meaningfully considered in isolation from their materials and surfaces, or vice versa, or from the people who have a relationship with them. There are several other categorisation systems in existence, which when used all together may better express the complexity of people and their relationships with objects e.g. Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981), Battarbee and Mattelmaki (2004), Thompson, (2004). Our initial matrix (figure 7) aims to add to these by specifically focusing on materials, their surfaces and the ‘effects and affect’ of time.

Conclusions: materials, temporality and custodianship

From our initial investigation we are confident that the surface evolution of a material/object can be interpreted as a positive enhancement. In these circumstances, the surface is able to provide a series of sensual and metaphoric triggers of emotional response to and subsequent valuing of an object. This goes significantly beyond either the object’s operational parameters or intrinsic value. In these situations, the relationship between the individual and the object clearly extends beyond the simple possessive state of ownership – instead of owner we may become custodian.

If we buy a new product from a shop, we expect it to be perfect – ‘out of the box’ – as we see this inviolate state as part of what we have paid for. This transaction initiates an inferred responsibility regarding the maintenance of the product’s ‘showroom’ finish. If later it becomes scratched, dented or broken has its purchaser failed as an owner? Or is damage proof of the rights that accompany ownership? Like some other man-made materials plastics have a particularly low level of custodial appeal. Although in existence everywhere as useful

objects, plastic is a transient, often unnoticed or unadmired presence in our lives. And yet paradoxically it is strongly associated with newness and ‘out of the box’ perfection and so damage – a scratch, a chip- will often lead quickly to disposal. Considering plastic’s ubiquity this indicates a serious loss of opportunity for more positive experiences.

Clearly, there is a continuity gap between older cherished objects and the newly purchased product. Can designers help to bridge the continuity gap? ‘Patina’ describes an altered physical surface but also implies provenance or authenticity, it is one of the ways by which we judge the maturation of the object over time. Wabi sabi shows us that this cannot be faked. False patina tries to achieve maturation in an instant, and is therefore unconvincing and unable to generate respect and a long-term custodial relationship. But we believe that designers can create new materials that will have a more sustained temporal affect. Our research has indicated a number of possible ways forward.

Looking at the world with a wabi sabi vision reveals opportunities all around us, to study and understand time’s affect on the world. Rather than copy it as fake patina, designers need to reapply these processes of change in challenging ways, in order to hope to bring the potential for maturity to newness.

*How sad: cherry blossoms
turn to clouds that
come to greet me.*

Kari.

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